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COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

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D3.2 Report on the determination of the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Fast pyrolysis is an efficient process to convert solid biomass to liquid bio-oils. The EU funded SmartCHP project is aiming to develop a smart and flexible small-scale combined heat and power (CHP) system running on fast-pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO). In SmartCHP system, FPBO is used in the stationary diesel engines for power generation. However, the special physical and chemical properties of FPBO, such as high viscosity and low chemical reactivity, limit its direct application in diesel engines.

To broaden our knowledge on FPBO combustion under engine-like conditions, the fundamental spray combustion characteristics of wood-based FPBO (reference), FPBO/alcohol blends, FPBO blended with ignition improver, and FPBO from different biomass origins are experimentally investigated in this deliverable. A combustion research unit (CRU) equipped with the heavy-fuel oil injection system and high-temperature chamber is employed to provide the well-defined initial ambient conditions for fuel spray combustion. It also has a borescope port which accommodates to the high-speed diagnostics on fuel spray flames. The pressure-based heat release analysis is used to determine fuel ignition and combustion characteristics, while the high-speed imaging technique is adopted to visualize flame natural luminosity during the fuel spray combustion.

Results show that the flame natural luminosity of FPBO is much lower than diesel. At the injection pressure of 300 bar, the atomization quality of FPBO is quite poor, leading to lots of discrete soot parcels, and some of nozzle orifices are quickly blocked within several injections. The increase of FPBO injection pressure could obviously improve the atomization quality and nozzle durability. The fuel dribble phenomenon for FPBO is alleviated compared with diesel. For FPBO/alcohol blends, 30% ethanol addition could significantly reduce the flame natural luminosity, while 30% n-butanol addition could improve the ignitability. Adding ignition improver, Beraid, into FPBO/ethanol blends could improve the ignitability, extending the lower limit of required ambient temperature for complete combustion. For FPBO samples made from different biomass origins, the sample from sunflower husks has both the lowest ignitability and sooting tendency, while FPBO made from miscanthus has the highest sooting tendency.

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Terminology

Abbreviation	Description
ASOE	after the start of energizing
ASOI	after the start of injection
BDC	bottom death center
CMOS	complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor
CRU	combustion research unit
CVCC	Constant-volume combustion chamber
FPBO	fast pyrolysis bio-oil
HFO	heavy-fuel oil
HRR	heat release rate
LOL	lift-off length
MFB	mass fraction burned
NL	natural luminosity
PEG	polyethylene glycol
SOE	start of energizing
SOI	start of injection
TDC	top dead center

1. Introduction

Fast pyrolysis is an efficient process to convert solid biomass to liquid biofuel. The organic feedstocks are first heated rapidly to 450–600 °C in the absence of oxygen. After a short residence time of several seconds, the formed vapor is quickly condensed to a liquid product, called fast pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) [1,2]. The SmartCHP project is aiming to develop a smart and flexible small-scale combined heat and power (CHP) system running on FPBO.

Diesel engine has fast response as well as high thermal efficiency, and hence it is used as the electric generator in the SmartCHP system. However, the physical and chemical properties of FPBO differ from commercial diesel, so that the diesel engine needs major modifications to facilitate FPBO applications. The high acidity of FPBO (pH 2-3) demands the fuel supply and injection system of diesel engine to use metallic corrosion-resistant materials, such as stainless steel [3,4]. FPBO has high viscosity which generally requires fuel preheating in engine application to increase fluidity [5,6]. The chemical reactivity of FPBO is much lower compared to diesel, which makes the major engine modification necessary to increase the compression ratio or the temperature of intake air or both [5–7]. Moreover, its tendency to polymerize at elevated temperatures may lead to nozzle clogging and coking, since the large weight molecules formed from polymerization are prone to precipitate from the liquid phase [2,8].

Fuel upgrade is also a realistic way to fuel diesel engines with FPBO. There are a number of upgrade methods: physically, chemically and catalytically [1]. Compared with other upgrading methods, blending the FPBO with a higher-quality base-fuel is a common solution to fuel an unmodified diesel engine with FPBO. Due to the polar properties of FPBO, low carbon alcohols, such as ethanol and n-butanol, are widely used to mix with FPBO [9–11]. Blending with alcohols brings many benefits for FPBO, such as reducing its viscosity as well as surface tension and curbing polymerization. All these effects could improve the stability and atomization quality of the fuel blends. However, due to the low chemical reactivity of both FPBO and alcohols, it is still necessary to make proper engine modification [5,6] or to add high reactivity compositions [11–15].

Although it is promising to fuel diesel engine with FPBO, in most of existing experimental studies, the mass fraction of FPBO was limited lower than 30%. A few studies achieved using high FPBO content (>70%) in the modified diesel engine [5,6]. However, there is still a lack of fundamental investigation of FPBO spray combustion characteristics under engine-like conditions. In the previous SmartCHP Deliverable 3.2 [16], we performed investigation on the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO and its blends using the combustion research unit (CRU). Based on the constant-volume combustion chamber (CVCC) technology, CRU can provide well-defined and quiescent boundary conditions for fuel spray combustion. Furthermore, the optical access from the bottom adaptor of CRU is achieved in this study. The spray combustion characteristics of FPBO and its blends are studied through the high-speed imaging of the broadband flame natural luminosity. The present work is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the experimental methodology, including the CRU setup, high-speed imaging method, image processing and tested conditions. Then, the results are analyzed and discussed in Section 3. Finally, the general conclusions are detailed in section 4.

2. Methodology

2.1 Experimental setup

The combustion research unit (CRU) is employed to study the combustion process of FPBO and its blends under engine-like conditions. The basic working principle of CRU has been introduced in the previous SmartCHP Deliverable 3.2 [16]. Compared with standard CRU, the following three improvements are implemented in the CRU to carry out the experimental research in this report:

1. The standard diesel fuel injection system is upgraded to a sophisticated heavy-fuel oil (HFO) injection system to adapt for the high viscosity fuels.
2. The standard chamber is upgraded to a high-temperature chamber to realize a higher ambient temperature for fuel autoignition.
3. The bottom adapter with a small optical window is installed in CRU to perform high-speed imaging of fuel spray flames through a borescope.

Figure 2.1 Schematic overview of the combustion chamber equipped with borescope (left) and the heavy-fuel injection system (right) in the CRU.

As shown in the right panel of Figure 2.1, the dual circuit is built in HFO injection system. The working medium in control circuit, diesel, is pressurized in the pressure amplifier to up to 1000 bar. Then, part of the pressurized diesel is supplied to the accumulator, which maintains a high pressure in the upper end of the injector plunger to ensure that the nozzle valve is properly closed between injection cycles. In fuel circuit, the tested HFO sample (in this study, FPBO and its blends are tested) is first pressurized in the fuel pressurizer driven by the high-pressure diesel, and then supplied to HFO injector. In the HFO injector, both the injector body and the nozzle are manufactured to have a fuel return hole, which is used to conveniently drain and flush the HFO fuel lines. The isolation of the HFO sample and the vulnerable pressure amplifier improves the stability and durability of the fuel supply

system. The nozzle used in HFO injector is the same with that in as the standard Bosch CRIP2 injector, which has 7 holes with the orifice diameter of 160 μm and the umbrella angle of 158°. Additionally, the minimum sample volume required by the HFO injection system is only 30 mL, much smaller than the requirement of the standard injection system (400 mL). The HFO injection system can provide fuel injection pressures ranging between 200 – 1000 bar.

Table 2.1 CRU operation parameters before and after upgrade

Parameter	Before upgrade	After upgrade
Chamber volume [mL]	475	300
Chamber wall temperature [°C]	300 – 590	300 – 750
Initial chamber pressure [bar]	20 – 70	20 – 70
Injection pressure [bar]	200 – 1600	200 – 1000
Injection duration [μs]	0 – 1500	0 – 1000
Minimum fuel volume [mL]	400	30

The left panel of Figure 2.1 shows the dimensions of CRU high-temperature chamber. It is smaller than the standard chamber but able to provide the chamber wall temperature up to 750 °C. Table 2.1 compares CRU operation parameters before and after upgrade. In the standard chamber, there are two thermocouples installed inside the different height of the chamber side wall, to measure the chamber wall temperatures. Correspondingly, according to the temperature readings, CRU controls the heating power of the two electric heaters to limit the vertical non-uniformity of wall temperature within 1 °C. However, due to the reduced dimensions, there is only one electric heater in high-temperature chamber. Hence, the temperature reading from the upper thermocouple is used as chamber wall temperature. During the experiments, the temperature difference measured by two thermocouples is below 10 °C.

The fuel pressure and chamber pressure are recorded by CRU at a rate of 50 kHz (intervals of 0.02 ms), from the start of injection (SOI) to about 45 ms after that. It is noteworthy that the period between start of the energizing (SOE) and start of the injection (SOI), i.e., injector hydraulic delay, is 0.34 ms for the HFO injector. The chamber pressure data output by CRU are processed to calculate the heat release rate (HRR) and mass fraction burned (MFB) profiles to characterize the ignition and combustion processes of tested fuels. The detailed data processing procedures of CRU chamber pressure data were detailed in Refs. [11,16].

2.2 High-speed imaging of fuel spray flames

A high-speed camera (Photron Fastcam SA3, single channel, 12-bit depth, maximum resolution of 1024x1024 pixels under frame rate of 1000 fps) equipped with a borescope (angle of view of 48 °C) is used to record the broadband flame natural luminosity of fuel spray flames through the small optical window of the CRU bottom adapter. The camera is synchronously triggered by the injector SOE signal.

Figure 2.2 shows the image of the 5x5 mm chess board shot by the high-speed camera equipped with the borescope. The target chess board is placed towards the

borescope with the same distance between the injector nozzle tip and the borescope in CRU experiments. The diameter of visible range of the target chess board is about 60 mm, smaller than the chamber diameter (85 mm), meaning that the direct flame/wall impingement cannot be observed using such borescope. Regarding image distortion, the barrel distortion in most part of the field of view is inapparent, so that the image distortion is not corrected in this report. However, it is worth noting that the distortion in periphery is nonnegligible.

Figure 2.2 An image of the 5x5 mm chess board shot by the high-speed camera equipped with the borescope (frame rate of 50 fps, image resolution of 1024x1024 pixels).

In CRU experiments, the energizing time of injector solenoid is limited by 1 ms, meaning the higher frame rate of high-speed imaging is desired for the better time resolution of flame visualization. However, limited by the performance of camera, the image resolution is reduced in case the frame rate is elevated. In this study, frame rate of 2000 fps with image resolution of 640x688 pixels is employed to record all 7 plumes of the fuel spray flames, while for better time resolution, frame rate of 10000 fps with image resolution of 512x144 pixels is also used to record one of the 7 plumes. Some examples can be found in the next subsection.

To avoid overexposure or underexposure, the exposure time of camera complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) sensor, i.e., the shutter, is adjusted to adapt to the different flame luminosity. For example, the higher sooting tendency of diesel generally leads to a higher natural luminosity, so that a shorter shutter of 25 μ s is adopted when recording diesel spray flames.

2.3 Image processing

The 12-bit grayscale images shot by high-speed camera are processed with Matlab scripts. As shown in Figure 2.3, the raw image is first processed by background subtraction, then colored by the jet colormap, and finally labelled with the frame moment. Red color denotes high luminosity areas while blue color denotes low luminosity areas. The overexposure areas are denoted by dark red, and the nonluminous background areas are denoted by dark blue. Compared with the raw grayscale images, the processed false-color images can clearly present flame structure in the whole luminosity range.

Figure 2.3 An example of image processing for flame images with 7 plumes. Left: a raw image from high-speed camera with frame rate of 2000 fps, resolution of 640x688 pixels, and shutter of $25\text{ }\mu\text{s}$. Right: the false-color image after processing. Injector and liquid fuel spray plumes are also visible.

Figure 2.4 An example of image processing for flame images with single plume. Left: the raw and false-color images with frame rate of 10000 fps, resolution of 512x144 pixels, and shutter of $25\text{ }\mu\text{s}$. Right: cumulative pixel value as a function of time for the 5 repeat tests.

Figure 2.4 shows the single-plume flame images recorded with the frame rate of 10000 fps. Besides the above-mentioned image processing procedures, the cumulative flame natural luminosity (NL) is calculated for single-plume flame

images by adding up all pixel values in each frame. The right panel of Figure 2.4 shows the cumulative flame NL as a function of time for the 5 repeat tests their averaged result.

The broadband flame natural luminosity shot by high-speed camera is generally dominated by soot radiation. However, it could be challenging to estimate the actual distribution of soot in CRU by viewing the flame natural luminosity images as shown in Figure 2.3 and Figure 2.4 for the following reasons [17]:

1. From an imaging perspective, the light captured by a pixel of the CMOS sensor is not from a single point source, but from an accumulation of light emitted from all soot particles that propagate toward the pixel, i.e., from along a line of sight.
2. The temperature of soot particles is important, hotter particles emitting with greater intensity, while the temperature distribution in fuel spray flame is of course non-uniform.
3. The increased soot concentration at a certain temperature also elevates local image brightness.

There is inherent uncertainty whether the brightness variation over the field-of-view is due to variations in local temperature or in soot concentration or both. Hence in this study, the cumulative flame natural luminosity is calculated to reflect an overall estimation in natural luminosity of fuel spray flames. It is noted that besides temperature and soot concentration, the cumulative flame natural luminosity is also influenced by the total area of (soot) flame in each image.

2.4 Tested fuels and conditions

Table 2.2 Fuel properties of diesel, FPBO, n-butanol, and ethanol

Property	Unit	Diesel	FPBO ^(a)	n-Butanol	Ethanol
LHV	MJ/kg	42.6	16.4	33.1	28.9
	MJ/L	34.9	19.2	26.8	22.5
Density	kg/L	0.82	1.17	0.81	0.78
C	wt%	85.0	42.8	64.8	52.2
H	wt%	12.6	7.8	13.6	13.0
O	wt%	-	49.2	21.6	34.8
Water	wt%	-	24.1	-	-
Solid	wt%	-	0.04	-	-
Viscosity (40 °C)	cSt	2.7	21	3.1	1.1
pH	-	-	2.6	-	-
Cetane number	-	54.8	-	17	8

(a) Properties of FPBO are based on Ref. [5]

The purpose of the experiments carried out in this study is to investigate the fundamental spray combustion characteristics of the following fuels:

1. Wood-based FPBO and diesel as reference fuels
2. FPBO with small addition (up to 30%) of alcohols (ethanol or n-butanol)

3. FPBO with addition of the cetane improver, Beraid
4. FPBO from different biomass origins.

Table 2.2 shows the properties of diesel, FPBO, n-butanol and ethanol. Besides these fuels, an ignition improver, Beraid (poly-ethylene-glycol derivative from Akzo Nobel), is also used to enhance the chemical reactivity with FPBO. For convenience, the detailed components of tested fuels are shown in the individual tables in each subsection of Section 3.

Table 2.3 Typical test conditions in CRU

Parameter	Value
Chamber wall temperature, T_{wall} [°C]	750
Initial chamber pressure, p_{init} [bar]	50
Injection pressure, p_{inj} [bar]	900
Injection duration, τ [μ s]	1000

Other typical test conditions in CRU are listed in Table 2.3. FPBO has a low chemical reactivity and consequently, both elevated engine compression ratio and increased inlet air temperature are normally required in engine application. In this study, the chamber wall temperature of CRU is set to its upper limit, 750 °C, to approach the in-cylinder temperature at top death center (TDC) of real engine. However, to evaluate the improvement of cetane improver addition, the chamber wall temperature is swept from 750 °C to 600 °C for FPBO/Beraid blends. For reference fuels and FPBO/alcohol blends, parametric studies on injection pressures (300, 600 and 900 bar) are also implemented. The initial chamber pressure is fixed at 50 bar for all the test cases.

3. Results and discussion

This section reports the results of heat release analysis and high-speed flame visualization for FPBO and blends. The results of the reference fuels, wood-based FPBO and diesel, are discussed in Section 3.1. The effects of ethanol and n-butanol additions are presented in Section 3.2. Section 3.3 shows the results of ignition improver, Beraid addition at different chamber wall temperatures. Finally, Section 3.4 compares 4 FPBO samples made from different biomass origins

3.1 Reference fuels: pure FPBO and diesel

Figure 3.1 shows the flame natural luminosity (NL) images of diesel sprays at 3 injection pressures, and Figure 3.2 shows the corresponding heat release rate (HRR) as well as mass fraction burned (MFB) profiles. At the injection pressure of 300 bar, the injected diesel autoignites between 1.0-1.5 ms after the start of energizing (ASOE). At 1.5 ms, the quasi-steady lifted diesel spray flames can be observed. The intense flame natural luminosity also illuminates the liquid sprays upstream. After the end of injection, the lifted spray flames trace back to near-nozzle regions, which is called combustion recession. Fuel injection ends up between 1.5 and 2.0 ms, but after that, a relatively severe fuel dribble phenomenon happens and lasts for several milliseconds.

Figure 3.1 Development of diesel spray flames at different injection pressure conditions (300, 600 and 900 bar).

With the increase of injection pressure, the ignition delay of diesel spray is shortened and the lift-off length (LOL) of the soot flames is increased. From HRR profile, the two-stage combustion of diesel can be observed at the injection pressures of 600 and 900 bar: the premixed combustion followed by the diffusion-controlled combustion. The premixed combustion is caused by the autoignition of

the initially injected diesel which is well mixed with the entrained ambient air before combustion. Since the chamber wall temperature is set at a high value (750 °C), only a small amount of diesel is injected before autoignition, leading to the HRR peak of the premixed combustion is lower than that of the diffusion-controlled combustion. End-of-injection fuel dribble also happens at higher injection pressure, but according to the HRR and MFB profiles, it seems that higher injection pressure could curb fuel dribble. Previous study shows that the dribbling process is primarily governed by the needle closing speed instead of the injection velocity [18]. Therefore, it is inferred that the needle closing speed of HFO injector increases with the rise of injection pressure.

Figure 3.2 Heat release rate (HRR, top panel), mass fraction burned (MFB, middle panel), and cumulative natural luminosity (cumulative NL, bottom panel) profiles as a function of time after start of energizing (ASOE) for diesel at 3 injection pressures. The test conditions are the same with Figure 3.1. The blue and magenta vertical dash lines denote the moments for start of energizing (SOE) and start of injection (SOI), respectively.

Pure wood-based FPBO is tested at the injection pressures of 300 bar and 900 bar. The total of 10 injections are implemented at 300 bar, but some of the 7 nozzle orifices are quickly blocked within several injections. Figure 3.3 shows the last 5 injections of FPBO at 300 bar. In the 5th injection, 3 orifices have been fully blocked and one orifice is half blocked. Till the 10th injection, there are only 2 orifices keeping working. This is caused by the special properties of FPBO compared to diesel. On one hand, it has solid/ash contents which is prone to blocking nozzle orifice. On the other hand, because the CRU chamber keeps heating during the whole experiments, the fuel temperature in the sac of nozzle is relatively high (above 150 °C in estimation), which aggravates the polymerization tendency of FPBO and precipitates the large solid molecules from the liquid phase.

Figure 3.3 FPBO spray flames of 5 continuous tests at injection pressure of 300 bar.

Figure 3.4 Comparison of diesel and FPBO spray flames at injection pressure of 300 bar.

Figure 3.4 compares the spray combustion processes of diesel and FPBO at the injection pressure of 300 bar. The flame natural luminosity of FPBO is much lower than diesel, meaning that the lower sooting tendency. However, there are lots of discrete soot parcels in FPBO spray flames, indicating that the atomization quality of FPBO is much poorer than diesel. These soot parcels need longer time to be oxidized after the end of injection. Interestingly, the fuel dribble phenomenon for

FPBO is not obvious. This could be because the fuel remaining in the nozzle sac after the end of injection is difficult to dribble due to the high viscosity as well as surface tension of FPBO.

Figure 3.5 Comparison of diesel and FPBO spray flames at injection pressure of 900 bar.

Figure 3.6 HRR, MFB, and cumulative NL profiles as a function of time ASOE for diesel and FPBO at injection pressure of 900 bar. The test conditions are the same with Figure 3.5. In bottom panel, the cumulative NL profile of diesel is doubled since the shutter used for diesel is half of that for FPBO.

The nozzle blocking problem is alleviated by using a higher injection pressure (900 bar). None of the nozzle orifices is significantly blocked at 900 bar within around 30 injections. Figure 3.5 compares flame natural luminosity images of FPBO and diesel at the injection pressure of 900 bar, and Figure 3.6 shows the corresponding HRR, MFB and cumulative NL profiles. There are just a few soot parcels surrounding the spray plumes and all soot parcels are quickly consumed after the end of

injection, indicating that the atomization quality of FPBO is obviously improved at higher injection pressure. Compared to diesel, the ignition delay of FPBO is longer, while the lift-off length is shorter.

3.2 FPBO with addition of alcohol

In this subsection, different amount of ethanol or n-butanol is blended with FPBO and the spray combustion characteristics of these fuel blends are tested. Table 3.1 shows the nomenclature and composition of these blends.

Table 3.1 Nomenclature and composition of FPBO/alcohol blends

Nomenclature	FPBO [wt%]	Ethanol [wt%]	n-Butanol [wt%]
F+E10	90	10	-
F+E30	70	30	-
F+nB10	90	-	10
F+nB30	70	-	30

FPBO, $T_{wall}=750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $p_{inj}=900\text{ bar}$ (shutter: 50 μs , pixel value doubled)

F+E10, $T_{wall}=750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $p_{inj}=900\text{ bar}$ (shutter: 100 μs)

F+E30, $T_{wall}=750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $p_{inj}=900\text{ bar}$ (shutter: 100 μs)

Figure 3.7 Spray flames of FPBO/ethanol blends with ethanol mass fraction of 0%, 10%, and 30%.

Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8 show the effects of ethanol addition on FPBO combustion processes. Small amount of ethanol addition (0%-30%) has negligible influence on heat release rate, while it reduces the flame natural luminosity significantly. This means that ethanol addition could effectively inhibit the soot formation. Moreover, the atomization quality could be also improved since ethanol addition could reduce the viscosity as well as surface tension [5].

Figure 3.8 HRR, MFB, and cumulative NL profiles as a function of time ASOE for FPBO blended with different percentages of ethanol (0%, 10%, and 30%). The test conditions are the same with Figure 3.7. In bottom panel, the cumulative NL profile of FPBO is doubled since the shutter used for FPBO is half of that for FPBO/ethanol blends.

Figure 3.9 HRR, MFB, and cumulative NL profiles as a function of time ASOE for FPBO blended 30% ethanol at 3 injection pressures (300, 600, 900 bar). Other test conditions are the same with Figure 3.10.

For FPBO+30%Ethanol, effects of injection pressure are also investigated, as shown in Figure 3.9. Similar to the conclusions drawn from diesel combustion, the increase of injection pressure could shorten the ignition delay and alleviate fuel dribbling after the end of injection.

Figure 3.10 Spray flames of FPBO/n-butanol blends with n-butanol mass fraction of 0%, 10%, and 30%.

Figure 3.11 HRR, MFB, and cumulative NL profiles as a function of time ASOE for FPBO blended with different percentages of n-butanol (0%, 10%, and 30%). The test conditions are the same with FPBO+30%Ethanol in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.10 and Figure 3.11 show the effects of n-butanol addition on FPBO combustion processes. The small amount of n-butanol addition could slightly improve fuel ignitability. However, compared to ethanol, n-butanol addition has less influence on inhibiting soot formation. This is because the oxygen content in n-butanol is about 2/3 of that in ethanol (see Table 2.2).

3.3 FPBO with addition of ignition improver

The effects of Beraid addition into FPBO blends are investigated in this subsection. Beraid is first designed for burning ethanol in the diesel engine, and hence it works as both ignition improver and lubricator. Similar to FPBO, Beraid has a high viscosity and previous studies indicated that the direct Beraid addition into FPBO could not get pronounced improvement [6,16]. Consequently, the effects of Beraid addition are tested by varying Beraid content in FPBO/ethanol/Beraid ternary blends. Table 3.2 shows the nomenclature and composition of the blends.

Table 3.2 Nomenclature and composition of FPBO/ethanol/Beraid blends

Nomenclature	FPBO [wt%]	Ethanol [wt%]	Beraid [wt%]
F+E30	70	30	-
F+E25+Be5	70	25	5
F+E20+Be10	70	20	10
F+E15+Be15	70	15	15

Figure 3.12 Spray flames of FPBO/ethanol/Beraid ternary blends with fixed FPBO content (70%) and different Beraid content (0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%) at 750 °C (left) and 650 °C (right).

Figure 3.12 and Figure 3.13 show the combustion process of FPBO/ethanol/Beraid ternary blends with different Beraid content at two chamber wall temperatures (750

and 650 °C). Without Beraid addition, the combustion of FPBO+30%Ethanol is worsened when the chamber wall temperature decreases by 100 °C, e.g., the reduced final fuel conversion rate. At higher temperature, Beraid addition could slightly improve the fuel ignitability, while at lower temperature, this effect becomes more noticeable. This means that adding Beraid could extend the lower limit of required ambient temperature for the complete combustion of FPBO.

Figure 3.13 HRR, MFB, and cumulative NL profiles as a function of time ASOE for FPBO/ethanol/Beraid ternary blends with different Beraid percentages (0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%). The test conditions are the same with Figure 3.12 (left: $T_{wall}=750$ °C, right: $T_{wall}=650$ °C).

3.4 FPBO from different biomass origins

Different FPBO samples made from different biomass origins are also studied. Table 3.3 shows the nomenclatures for the FPBO samples from 4 different biomass origins: wood, sawmill residue, sunflower husks, and miscanthus.

Table 3.3 Nomenclature for FPBO from different biomass origins

FPBO nomenclature	Biomass origin
FPBO	Wood
FPBO _b	Sawmill residue
FPBO _c	Sunflower husks
FPBO _d	Miscanthus

Figure 3.14 Spray flames of diesel and 4 types of FPBO samples.

Figure 3.15 HRR, MFB, and cumulative NL profiles as a function of time ASOE for diesel and 4 types of FPBO samples. The test conditions are the same with Figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15 show the combustion processes of diesel and 4 types of FPBO samples. From HRR profiles, it is indicated that at 750 °C, the ignitability among FPBO, FPBO_b and FPBO_d are similar, while FPBO_c has a longer ignition delay, i.e., $FPBO \approx FPBO_b \approx FPBO_d > FPBO_c$. In our previous Deliverable 3.2 [16], these four FPBO samples with addition of 30% n-butanol were tested in the CRU using the standard chamber (wall temperature of 590 °C), and the results showed that the order of fuel ignitability was $FPBO \approx FPBO_d \gg FPBO_b > FPBO_c$. The differences between previous (FPBO samples with 30% n-butanol addition at 590 °C) and present (pure FPBO samples at 750 °C) studies indicate:

1. FPBO (wood) and FPBO_d (miscanthus) have higher ignitability in the whole temperature range of 590–750 °C, while FPBO_c (sunflower husks) has the lowest ignitability consistently.
2. At 590 °C, the ignitability of FPBO_b (sawmill residue) is much lower than FPBO and FPBO_d, while this gap is considerably reduced at 750 °C.

FPBO is the complex mixture of thousands of chemical compositions. On one hand, each composition has different evaporation as well as ignition characteristics. On the other hand, the different biomasses, or even the different production batches, have influence on FPBO compositions. Hence, it is challenging to predict the autoignition process for FPBO at low temperature. Fortunately, according to chemical kinetics of combustion reaction, large hydrocarbon molecules are prone to direct cracking at high temperature [19]. Consequently, the increase of either intake air temperature or compression ratio could significantly shorten ignition delay and reduce the gap among different FPBO samples. This was also confirmed in previous engine experiments [5]. van de Beld et al. tested FPBO in two modified diesel engines with different compression ratio, 18 and 22, respectively. A basic thermodynamic calculation is performed in Table 3.4 to connect temperatures at TDC and BDC with the polytropic process correlation. The experiments using CRU high-temperature chamber (750 °C) can well reproduce the in-cylinder condition for 100-°C air preheating in a diesel engine with compression ratio of 18, approaching the temperature range for engine stable operation running on FPBO (80–220 °C) [5].

Table 3.4 Thermodynamic estimation of the air temperature at top death center (TDC) and bottom death center (BDC) in the diesel engine.

Polytropic process: $T_{TDC} = T_{BDC} \epsilon^{\gamma-1}$			
Polytropic index, γ	Compression ratio, ϵ	T_{TDC}	T_{BDC}
1.35	18	1023 K (750 °C)	372 K (99 °C)
	18	863 K (590 °C)	313 K (40 °C)
	22	1023 K (750 °C)	346 K (73 °C)
	22	863 K (590 °C)	292 K (19 °C)

In practice, almost all the chemical energy of the injected fuel is released during the combustion processes at 750 °C. However, from MFB profiles, the nominal final fuel conversion rate of FPBO_d is lower than the other three samples. This is because the same volumetric LHV is used for all FPBO samples. Hence, it seems that that the volumetric LHV of FPBO_d is about 80% of the other three samples. But

interestingly, in our previous Deliverable 3.2 [16], the test results of four FPBO samples with addition of 30% n-butanol showed that the order of volumetric LHV was $FPBO_d \gg FPBO \approx FPBO_b \approx FPBO_c$. Besides the objective differences in LHV, there are still several possible reasons:

1. Among the tests of four FPBO samples, $FPBO_d$ is the final tested sample using the same nozzle, meaning that the injection volume is possible to be changed considering the solid content and polymerization tendency of FPBO.
2. In previous tests at chamber wall temperature of 590 °C, the ignition delay was quite long, so that the spray/wall interaction was unavoidable, meaning that the liquid film was possible to adhere on the chamber wall, leading to the deviation in MFB calculation.

As shown in cumulative NL profiles, all FPBO samples have lower sooting tendency compared to diesel. While the intensities of flame natural luminosity among the four samples are distinct: $FPBO_d > FPBO > FPBO_b > FPBO_c$. The potential factors influencing natural luminosity include:

1. oxygen content, affecting soot formation directly;
2. water content, influencing flame temperature;
3. solid content, working as nucleus of condensation;
4. viscosity and surface tensions, affecting liquid breakup and atomization.

Therefore, more in-depth analysis could be performed with the combination of accurate physicochemical properties of FPBO samples.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a combustion research unit equipped with a heavy-fuel oil injection system and high-temperature chamber is used to investigate the spray combustion characteristics of FPBO and blends using the high-speed imaging of flame natural luminosity. The wood-based FPBO and diesel are first tested as references at chamber wall temperature of 750 °C and initial pressure of 50 bar. Then, the effects of ethanol addition and n-butanol addition are studied. The influence of ignition improver addition at lower chamber wall temperature is also performed. Finally, four FPBO samples made from wood, sawmill residue, sunflower husks and miscanthus are compared. The main findings from this study can be concluded as follows.

- Compared with diesel, FPBO has lower sooting tendency and alleviate end-of-injection dribble, while its atomization quality at the injection pressure of 300 bar is quite poorer, leading to lots of discrete soot parcels and severe blockings of nozzle orifices.
- The increase of FPBO injection pressure to 900 bar could improve the atomization quality, ignitability, and nozzle durability.
- Adding 30% ethanol into FPBO could significantly reduce the flame natural luminosity, while 30% n-butanol addition could improve the ignitability.
- The increase of Beraid content in FPBO/ethanol/Beraid ternary blends could improve the ignitability, especially extending the lower limit of the required ambient temperature for complete combustion.
- For FPBO samples made from different biomass origins, the sample from sunflower husks has both the lowest ignitability and sooting tendency, while FPBO made from miscanthus has the highest sooting tendency.

5. References

- [1] Bridgwater A V. Review of fast pyrolysis of biomass and product upgrading. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 2012;38:68–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2011.01.048>.
- [2] Broumand M, Albert-Green S, Yun S, Hong Z, Thomson MJ. Spray combustion of fast pyrolysis bio-oils: Applications, challenges, and potential solutions. *Prog Energy Combust Sci* 2020;79:100834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2020.100834>.
- [3] Kass MD, Armstrong BL, Kaul BC, Connatser RM, Lewis S, Keiser JR, et al. Stability, Combustion, and Compatibility of High-Viscosity Heavy Fuel Oil Blends with a Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil. *Energy and Fuels* 2020;34:8403–13. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.0c00721>.
- [4] Kass MD, Janke C, Connatser R, Lewis S, Keiser J, Theiss T. Compatibility Assessment of Elastomeric Infrastructure Materials with Neat Diesel and a Diesel Blend Containing 20 Percent Fast Pyrolysis Bio-oil. *SAE Int J Fuels Lubr* 2015;8:50–61. <https://doi.org/10.4271/2015-01-0888>.
- [5] van de Beld B, Holle E, Florijn J. The use of a fast pyrolysis oil – Ethanol blend in diesel engines for chp applications. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 2018;110:114–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2018.01.023>.
- [6] van de Beld B, Holle E, Florijn J. The use of pyrolysis oil and pyrolysis oil derived fuels in diesel engines for CHP applications. *Appl Energy* 2013;102:190–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2012.05.047>.
- [7] European Committee for Standardization. CEN/TR 17103 Fast pyrolysis bio-oil for stationary internal combustion engines - Quality determination. 2017.
- [8] Wang R, Ben H. Accelerated Aging Process of Bio-Oil Model Compounds: A Mechanism Study. *Front Energy Res* 2020;8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2020.00079>.
- [9] Lee S, Woo SH, Kim Y, Choi Y, Kang K. Combustion and emission characteristics of a diesel-powered generator running with N-butanol/coffee ground pyrolysis oil/diesel blended fuel. *Energy* 2020;206:118201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.118201>.
- [10] Lee S, Kim TY. Feasibility study of using wood pyrolysis oil-ethanol blended fuel with diesel pilot injection in a diesel engine. *Fuel* 2015;162:65–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2015.08.049>.
- [11] Wang Y, Han J, Maes N, Cuijpers M, Somers B. Ignition and Combustion Characteristics of N-Butanol and FPBO/N-Butanol Blends With Addition of Ignition Improver. *Front Energy Res* 2022;10:1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2022.832509>.
- [12] Alcala A, Bridgwater A V. Upgrading fast pyrolysis liquids: Blends of biodiesel and pyrolysis oil. *Fuel* 2013;109:417–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2013.02.058>.
- [13] Kim TY, Lee S, Kang K. Performance and emission characteristics of a high-compression-ratio diesel engine fueled with wood pyrolysis oil-butanol blended fuels. *Energy* 2015;93:2241–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.10.119>.
- [14] Kim TY, Lee SH. Combustion and emission characteristics of wood pyrolysis oil-butanol blended fuels in a DI diesel engine. *Int J Automot Technol* 2015;16:903–12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12239-015-0092-4>.
- [15] Lee S, Kim TY, Kang KY. A Feasibility Study of Using Pyrolysis Oil/Butanol

- Blended Fuel in a di Diesel Engine. SAE Tech Pap 2015;2015. <https://doi.org/10.4271/2015-24-2437>.
- [16] Wang Y, Somers B, Maes N. Report on the determination of the ignition and combustion characteristics of FPBO. SmartCHP Deliv 2021.
- [17] Hessel R, Yue Z, Reitz R, Musculus M, O'Connor J. Guidelines for Interpreting Soot Luminosity Imaging. SAE Int J Engines 2017;10:1174–92. <https://doi.org/10.4271/2017-01-0716>.
- [18] Moon S, Huang W, Li Z, Wang J. End-of-injection fuel dribble of multi-hole diesel injector: Comprehensive investigation of phenomenon and discussion on control strategy. Appl Energy 2016;179:7–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.06.116>.
- [19] You X, Egolfopoulos FN, Wang H. Detailed and simplified kinetic models of n-dodecane oxidation: The role of fuel cracking in aliphatic hydrocarbon combustion. Proc Combust Inst 2009;32 1:403–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2008.06.041>.

